

Five Properties of the Smarandache Double Factorial Function

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Abstract

In this paper some properties of the Smarandache double factorial function have been analyzed.

In [1], [2], [3] and [4] the Smarandache double factorial $Sdf(n)$ function is defined as the smallest number such that $Sdf(n)!!$ is divisible by n , where the double factorial by definition is given by [6]:

$m!! = 1 \times 3 \times 5 \times \dots \times m$, if m is odd;

$m!! = 2 \times 4 \times 6 \times \dots \times m$, if m is even.

In [2] several properties of that function have been analyzed. In this paper five new properties are reported.

1. $Sdf(p^{k+2}) = p^2$ where $p = 2 \cdot k + 1$ is any prime and k any integer

Let's consider the prime $p = 2k + 1$. Then:

$1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot \dots \cdot p \cdot \dots \cdot 3p \cdot \dots \cdot 5p \cdot \dots \cdot p^2 = m \cdot p^{k+2}$ where m is any integer.

This because the number of terms multiples of p up to p^2 are $k+1$ and the last term contains two times p .

Then p^2 is the least value such that $1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 9 \cdot \dots \cdot p^2$ is divisible by p^{k+2} .

2. $Sdf(p^2) = 3 \cdot p$ where p is any odd prime.

In fact for any odd p we have:

$$1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot \dots \cdot p \cdot \dots \cdot 3p = m \cdot p^2 \quad \text{where } m \text{ is any integer.}$$

$$3. \quad Sdf\left(k \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right)\right) = Sdf\left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right) \quad \text{where } n \text{ is any integer } > 1 \text{ and } k=3,5,7,9$$

Let's suppose that $Sdf\left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right) = m$ then:

$$1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot \dots \cdot m = a \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right) \quad \text{where } a \text{ is any integer. But in the previous}$$

multiplication there are factors multiple of 3,5,7 and 9 and then:

$$1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot \dots \cdot m = a' \cdot k \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right) \quad \text{where } a' \text{ is any integer and } k=3,5,7,9. \text{ Then:}$$

$$Sdf\left(k \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right)\right) = m = Sdf\left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right)$$

$$4. \quad Sdf\left(k \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right)\right) = Sdf\left(2 \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right)\right) \quad \text{where } n \text{ is any integer } > 1 \text{ and } k=2,4,6,8$$

Let's suppose that $Sdf\left(2 \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right)\right) = m$ then:

$$2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdot 8 \cdot \dots \cdot m = a \cdot 2 \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right) \quad \text{where } a \text{ is any integer. But in the previous}$$

multiplication there are factors multiple of 4, 6 and 8 and then:

$$2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdot 8 \cdot \dots \cdot m = a' \cdot 2 \cdot k \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9} \right) \text{ where } a' \text{ is any integer and } k=4,6,8.$$

Then:

$$Sdf\left(k \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right)\right) = m = Sdf\left(2 \cdot \left(\frac{10^n - 1}{9}\right)\right)$$

5. $Sdf(p^m) = (2 \cdot m - 1) \cdot p$ for $p \geq (2m - 1)$. Here m is any integer and p any odd prime.

This is a generalization of property number 2 reported above.

References.

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